

Estimation of Copper(I) with Chloramine-T or *N*-Bromosuccinimide

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Estimation of copper(I) in aqueous or acid media is difficult due to interference of atmospheric or dissolved oxygen¹ and as such the earlier work is very limited. The present authors suggest a simple, rapid method for visual and potentiometric estimation of copper(I) with chloramine-T or *N*-bromosuccinimide.

Results and Discussion

The visual and potentiometric titrations of copper(I) with chloramine-T are carried out in 2–12 *N* sulphuric, 2–8 *N* hydrochloric, 2–12 *N* phosphoric and 2–12 *N* acetic acid media. In visual titrations with DPA as indicator, sharp colour transition to intense ink-blue is observed at the equivalence point in 4–12 *N* sulphuric acid medium only and in the other media, either low values or no colour transition is observed. In potentiometric titrations, quantitative values are obtained in 2–12 *N* sulphuric (360 mV), 4–6 *N* hydrochloric (225 mV), 4–8 *N* phosphoric (250 mV) and acetic (200 mV) acid media. The visual and potentiometric estimations of copper(I) with *N*-bromosuccinimide are carried out in 2–8 *N* sulphuric, 1–4 *N* hydrochloric, 1–16 *N* phosphoric and 2–4 *N* acetic acid media. In visual titrations using thionine as indicator, analytical values are obtained in 2–4 *N* sulphuric, 4 *N* phosphoric acid only with sharp colour transition from light green to ink-blue at the end-point. In potentiometric estimations, accurate values are obtained in 2–8 *N* sulphuric (460 mV), 1–4 *N* hydrochloric (300 mV), 4–12 *N* phosphoric (400 mV) and acetic (450 mV) acid media.

It has been found that the results of estimation of Cu^I (24–61 mg) with chloramine-T (4 *N* H₂SO₄) and with *N*-bromosuccinimide (4 *N* H₂SO₄ and 4 *N* H₃PO₄) are in good agreement with that estimated by the standard method². The average error of estimation was found to be < 0.1%.

Stable potentials are attained immediately and a potential break of 360 mV for 0.04 ml 0.1 *N* chloramine-T and 460 mV for 0.04 ml 0.1 *N* of *N*-bromosuccinimide is observed at the equivalence point. Typical results are presented in Table 1 in different acid media. The average error of estimation is found to be less than 0.1%.

The above methods reported are simple, accurate, rapid and easy to be carried out at room temperature without the use of catalyst. Earlier methods involve the use of non-aqueous media or use of inert atmosphere throughout the

titration, with less accuracy. It has been found that the stability of copper(I) solutions is markedly improved upto 2 h without the use of carbon dioxide atmosphere when the solutions of copper(I) are made in an overall 2 *M* hydrochloric and 6 *M* phosphoric acid media. This advantage enriches the analytical application of copper(I) as reductometric reagent.

TABLE 1—POTENTIOMETRIC ESTIMATION OF Cu^I WITH CHLORAMINE-T AND *N*-BROMOSUCCINIMIDE IN DIFFERENT ACID MEDIA
Amount of Cu^I (mg)

Taken standard method*	Found present method	Relative error, %
(a) With chloramine-T :		
H ₂ SO ₄ medium (4 <i>N</i>) :		
24.38	24.37	-0.04
36.48	36.47	-0.03
48.74	48.74	Nil
60.67	60.67	Nil
HCl medium (4 <i>N</i>) :		
24.38	24.36	-0.08
36.48	36.49	0.03
48.74	48.75	0.02
60.67	60.68	0.02
H ₃ PO ₄ medium (4 <i>N</i>) :		
24.38	24.37	-0.04
36.48	36.47	-0.03
48.74	48.74	Nil
60.67	60.68	0.02
Acetic acid medium (4 <i>N</i>) :		
24.38	24.37	-0.04
36.48	36.50	0.05
48.74	48.75	0.02
60.67	60.68	0.02
(b) With <i>N</i> -bromosuccinimide :		
H ₂ SO ₄ medium (4 <i>N</i>) :		
20.64	20.64	Nil
31.85	31.87	0.06
42.69	42.67	-0.06
56.61	56.60	-0.02
HCl medium (4 <i>N</i>) :		
20.64	20.63	-0.05
31.86	35.85	-0.03
42.69	42.67	-0.06
56.61	56.62	0.02

Table-1 (contd.)

H ₃ PO ₄ medium (4 N) :		
20.64	20.64	Nil
31.86	31.85	-0.03
42.69	42.68	-0.02
56.61	56.62	0.02
Acetic acid medium (4 N) :		
20.64	20.65	0.05
31.86	31.85	-0.03
42.69	42.67	-0.06
56.61	56.62	0.02

*Ref. 2.

Experimental

Copper(I) chloride (AnalaR) was dissolved in concentrated HCl to give an overall 2 M strength and to which syrupy H₃PO₄ was added to give overall 6 M strength. The solution was made up with distilled water to give 0.1 N copper solution and standardised². A 0.1 N chloramine-T (AnalaR) solution was prepared in distilled water and standardised³. A 0.1 N N-bromosuccinimide (AnalaR) solution was prepared in distilled water and standardised⁴. A 0.2% indicator solution was made in distilled water. All other reagents used are of AnalaR grade. Potentiometric assembly (Pacfic-India) with calomel and platinum electrodes was used.

Procedure for estimation : To a mixture of 8 N H₂SO₄ (25 ml) and distilled water (15 ml) CO₂ was passed for 2-3 min. An aliquot (10 ml) of Cu^I solution and indicator (0.05 ml) were added and the solution of oxidant was run down from the micro-burette slowly. Diphenylamine was used as indicator with copper(I)/chloramine-T, when the colour changed from light green to intense ink-blue at the

equivalence point. Thionine was used as indicator with copper(I)/N-bromosuccinimide, when the colour changed from light green to ink-blue at the end-point.

Procedure for potentiometric estimation : A mixture of 8 N H₂SO₄ (25 ml) and distilled water (15 ml) were taken in a titration vessel having five-hole rubber stopper, one each for salt bridge, indicator electrode, microburette nozzle and two as inlet and outlet for CO₂ gas to expel any dissolved oxygen. Connections were made from indicator and calomel electrodes to the potentiometer to record potentials. A 0.1 N solution of chloramine-T or N-bromosuccinimide was run down from the microburette slowly and the stable potentials attained after each addition were recorded.

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